

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

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D2.1 Monitoring Frameworks overview

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D2.1 – Monitoring Frameworks overview

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
BD	The Birds Directive
BC	Barcelona Convention: Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean
BuC	Bucharest Convention: Convention on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
HD	The Habitats Directive
HELCOM	Helsinki Convention: Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area
IASR	The Invasive Alien Species Regulation
MSFD	The Marine Strategy Framework Directive
OSPAR	OSPAR Convention: Oslo and Paris Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
RLR	Restoration Law Regulation
WFD	The Water Framework Directive

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Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The EU's commitment to marine biodiversity protection is embedded in key strategies like the European Green Deal, the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and the Action Plan for Marine Ecosystems. Key EU legal instruments include directives such as the Birds and Habitats Directives, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, and recent regulations like the Restoration Law Regulation. For an overview of EU marine biodiversity law and policy frameworks, data requirements for each instrument were classified into 16 biological data types based on the MSFD Descriptors, following the methodology used in the OBAMA NEXT project. In parallel, a revised database of EU marine biodiversity monitoring programmes was created—drawing on MarBioMe and additional sources—which now includes 206 ongoing programmes, 14 of them citizen-science based. The Greater North Sea hosts the most programmes, while the Oceanic Northeast Atlantic has the fewest. Within the Mediterranean basin, the coverage of biodiversity monitoring programmes is more heterogeneous indicating the Adriatic Sea as the region with less coverage, and the Western Mediterranean Sea as the region being covered by more monitoring programmes. Key taxonomic groups surveyed include benthic invertebrates, phytoplankton, and fish, with less identified monitoring programmes on turtles and cephalopods. While older regulations provide comprehensive guidance for biological data needs, newer regulations like the Invasive Alien Species Regulation and Restoration Law Regulation rely on earlier frameworks. Additionally, sensitive groups such as macroalgae, seagrass, and turtles require additional monitoring programmes.

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1. EU marine biodiversity law and policy frameworks overview

Monitoring marine biodiversity is indispensable for conserving marine ecosystems, meeting legal obligations, and promoting sustainable use of marine resources. It forms the backbone of efforts to balance environmental protection with human activities in EU waters, ensuring resilience and sustainability in the face of growing environmental challenges. EU Commitments to maintain and improve marine biodiversity are included not only in marine-specific regulations but form part of high-level regional economic and environmental strategies including the European Green Deal (COM/2019/640), the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (COM/2020/380) and the EU Action Plan for Protecting and restoring marine ecosystems for sustainable and resilient fisheries (COM(2023)102).

Some of those EU key legal instruments had been identified in the proposal and after an exhaustive literature review and consultation of results from other projects (e.g. OBAMA NEXT: <https://obama-next.eu/>) the list of laws/regulations/conventions/directives, below, was chosen for further analysis based on their specifications relevant to marine biodiversity data:

- The Birds Directive (BD) [1979] (Directive 79/409/EEC) (Directive 2009/147/EC)
- The Habitats Directive (HD) [1992] (Council Directive 92/43/EEC)
- The Water Framework Directive (WFD) [2000] (Directive E 2000/60/EC)
- The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) [2008] (Directive 2008/56/EC)
- Common Fisheries Policy (Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013) (Regulation (EU) 2017/1004)
- The Invasive Alien Species Regulation (IASR) [2014] (Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014)
- Restoration Law Regulation (RSR) [2024] (Regulation (EU) 2024/1991)
- OSPAR Convention [1992]: (OSPAR) Oslo and Paris (OSPAR) Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
- Helsinki Convention [1992]: (HELCOM) Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area
- Barcelona Convention [1995]: (BC) Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean
- Bucharest Convention (BuC) [1992]: Convention on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution.

Next, and to assess EU marine biodiversity monitoring priorities for data collection, particular focus was given to the results reported in the OBAMA NEXT D6.1 deliverable: Review, analysis and crosswalk of the data requirements of key policies (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13981476>). That deliverable, considered four EU Directives and four Regional Seas Conventions and Action Plans listed above, as well as some guidance documents, aiming to safeguard and recover marine species and habitats within the European Union. To identify the data needs of selected instruments, the provisions of the main texts and their annexes were reviewed alongside their associated reporting templates. Then data needs for those instruments, were categorised under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) Descriptors (forming 11 categories) and each data need was categorized by the data type (physical, chemical and biological).

The crosswalk between the identified data needs of biological type, from those eight instruments reported in the OBAMA NEXT D6.1 deliverable, was performed in the scope of DTO-BioFlow Task 2.1 using Microsoft Excel (v16.0), and resulted in 16 categories of biological types of data need across those key legal instruments (Table 1), to which was added the review and analysis of two extra regulations (IASR and RLR) following the same methodology described above. Although biological data needs are well detailed in main texts and annexes of most of the first eight instruments, for the IASR and RLR the that type of data is more ambiguously mentioned.

Table 1. Categories of biological data needed to meet the standards on marine biodiversity monitoring of ten EU and international legal instruments.

Biological Data Categories	EU & international legal instruments										
	BD	HD	WFD	MSFD	OSPAR	HELCOM	BC	BuC	IASR	RLR	CFP
Species distribution	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Population demographics	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X		X
Habitat distribution		X			X		X			X	
Community composition	X		X	X	X	X		X		X	X
Change in species distribution	X	X		X					X	X	X
Change in Population demographics	X	X		X							X
Change in habitat distribution		X		X			X		X	X	
Change in community composition				X	X					X	X
Captive animals								X			
Bycatch				X	X	X	X	X			X
Catch		X				X	X	X			X
Fishing impacts				X			X	X			X
Impacts on biota				X		X	X		X		
Harmful algal blooms				X							
Mariculture								X			
Trophic structure				X	X		X			X	

2. EU biodiversity monitoring programmes overview

The current overview of the EU biodiversity monitoring programmes was built based on the EU project MarBioMe: Marine Biodiversity Monitoring Study in Europe (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7268400>), while also containing new programmes information taken from the MBON Europe inventory, from online searches, and by reaching out directly to programme coordinating entities. For the [DTO-BioFlow EU biodiversity monitoring programmes inventory](#), previous MarBioMe data were updated, and new parameters and categories defined to meet DTO-BioFlow requirements. Redundancies and errors were corrected, distinction between programmes and subprogrammes/stations was performed by grouping stations and subprogrammes within the main monitoring programme, and a colour code added to distinguish purely institutional programmes from partially or fully citizen science-based programmes. The DTO-BioFlow EU biodiversity monitoring programmes inventory comprises 206 ongoing programmes of which 14 are citizen science programmes (see Table 2 for a summary of all entries). From the identified programmes, 483 subprogrammes/stations have metadata available and 458 subprogrammes/stations have the raw data available although no evidence was found of these data complying with Darwin Core standards.

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Table 2. Summary of the DTO-BioFlow EU biodiversity monitoring programmes database entries.

Database summary	Total (numbers)
Ongoing Programmes	206
Lines (subprogrammes/stations)	630
Citizen science programmes	14
Running subprogrammes/stations	547
Subprogrammes/stations data updated in 2024	245
New subprogrammes/stations added	122

Regarding the EU and international legal instruments, the identified programmes in the DTO-BioFlow EU biodiversity monitoring programmes database complied with requirements mostly from the WFD and the MSFD (with 93 and 45 programmes, respectively) followed by CFP, BD and HD (Table 3).

Table 3. Number of monitoring programmes of the DTO-BioFlow database by EU and international legal instruments requirements complied.

EU & international legal instruments	Number of programmes
WFD	93
MSFD	45
CFP	17
BD	13
HD	10
IASR	2
HELCOM	2
OSPAR	1

The gathered information was used to plot the number of biodiversity monitoring programmes by ICES Ecoregions (<https://doi.org/10.17895/ices.advice.6014>). Results show the Greater North Sea as the region with the highest number of monitoring programmes, while the Oceanic Northeast Atlantic region shows the fewest monitoring programmes. Within the Mediterranean basin, the coverage of biodiversity monitoring programmes is more heterogeneous indicating the Adriatic Sea as the region with the fewest ones, and the Western Mediterranean Sea as the region with the most ones (Figures 1 and 2).

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Figure 1. Number of biodiversity monitoring programmes identified in the DTO-BioFlow EU biodiversity monitoring programmes database by ICES Ecoregions.

Figure 2. Visual representation of the number of biodiversity monitoring programmes identified in the DTO-BioFlow EU biodiversity monitoring programmes database by ICES Ecoregions.

Regarding the monitoring programmes identified in the DTO-BioFlow inventory by surveyed taxonomic groups, benthic invertebrates, phytoplankton, and fish are groups with more identified programmes compared to turtles and cephalopods (Figure 3). Based on the metadata, whereas, for the ICES Ecoregions the group with more identified programmes is phytoplankton in the Greater North Sea and the group with least identified programmes are the microbes in the Azores Ecoregion (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Relative contribution of monitoring programmes identified in the DTO-BioFlow EU biodiversity monitoring programmes database by surveyed taxonomic groups.

Figure 4. Number of monitoring programmes identified in the DTO-BioFlow EU biodiversity monitoring programmes database by surveyed taxonomic groups for each ICES Ecoregion.

3. Conclusions

Despite the broad coverage of biological data needs for monitoring marine biodiversity of the analysed legal instruments the most recent regulations (as the IASR and RLR) are not explicit and often refer to the specifications mentioned in former regulations such as the MSFD and the HD. Regarding the compiled monitoring programmes, there are clear regional differences in the number of programmes across ICES Ecoregions, with sensitive groups such as macroalgae, seagrass and turtles in need of more monitoring programmes.